

CHARACTERIZATION OF ENERGY ABSORPTION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP USING A NEW PLUG

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SUMMARY

A new type of plug, i.e. load-control attachment, was developed to control energy absorption capability of CFRP. Quasi-static and dynamic compression tests were performed. It was revealed that the energy absorption capability of unidirectional CFRP tube could be controlled arbitrary from 8 to 178kJ/kg by using the attachment.

Keywords: CFRP, Progressive crushing, energy absorption, crashworthiness

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is expected to be applied for crush energy absorbing structure of automobile because of its superior specific energy absorption as compared with metallic materials. Although a lot of researches on energy absorption characteristic of CFRP have been reported, design criterion has not been clarified because of its complexity of the fracture mechanism. Stacking sequence has large effect on energy absorption of CFRP, which also related strongly with its cross sectional feature [1-7]. Small usage of CFRP as automotive crush energy absorbing structure lies on the lack of the design guideline.

In this study, a new concept of plug, i.e. load-control attachment was proposed to resolve the problem. The new plug controls amount of fiber fracture of CFRP. By changing the attachment without changing constituent and stacking sequence of CFRP, required energy absorption can be obtained. A type of CFRP tube, therefore, is enough to be applied for various automobiles of different weights.

A total of 8 load-control attachments were produced to investigate the effect of curvature constraint on energy absorption capability of CFRP. A unidirectional CFRP tube was used in this study. Quasi-static compression test and dynamic crush test were performed for the CFRP with the load-control attachment. The effect of curvature constraint of the load-control attachment and impact speed on energy absorption capability of the CFRP were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and specimen

CFRP circular tube was fabricated by prepreg sheets PYROFIL#380 (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.) using autoclave molding method. Cure condition was followed by the manufacturer's instructions. The specimen had 50mm inner diameter and 80mm length. Stacking sequence of the specimen was $[12]_T$ which resulted in the thickness of approximately 3mm. No chamfer was machined on the specimen. The curvature on the load-control attachment initiated damage at tip of the specimen.

Load-control attachment

Energy absorption capability of CFRP tube is strongly affected by parameters such as fiber and matrix type, stacking sequence, and cross sectional feature, which resulted in the difficulty of appropriate design for each target. To resolve the problem, a new type of plug, i.e. load-control attachment, was proposed.

The load control attachment for CFRP circular tube was shown in Figure 1. The load-control attachment was composed of three parts. Component (1) and (2) constrains inner and outer curvature (R_i and R_o) of CFRP tube in the fracture process. These components were connected by component (3) with spacing of 3mm which was approximately the thickness of CFRP specimen. The component (3) had a knife-edge, which enable easy release of fractured CFRP from the load-control attachment.

The load-control attachment guides wall of CFRP tube under crushing by constraining both inner and outer surfaces of the wall. The amount of fiber fracture of CFRP may be controlled by changing the curvature of constrainers. Pairs of curvatures of the load-control attachments used in this paper were shown in Table 1.

Figure 1 Assembly drawing of load-control attachment for CFRP circular tube

Table 1 Pairs of curvatures of the load-control attachments

Attachment No.	0, 1	0, 2	0, 3	1, 4	2, 5	3, 6	4, 7	5, 8
R_o [mm]	0	0	0	1	2	3	4	5
R_i [mm]	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

Specific energy absorption

Specific energy absorption (E_s) was used to compare energy absorption efficiencies of CFRP tube with the load-control attachment.

$$E_s = \frac{P_a l}{m} \text{ kJ/kg} \quad (1)$$

Where P_a was average load, l and m were length and mass of CFRP specimen.

In this study, initial transition region from 0 to 10mm displacement was eliminated to calculate average load. The effect of curvatures of the load-control attachments on energy absorption capability of CFRP was evaluated.

Quasi-static compression test

Quasi-static compression tests were performed between parallel steel platens of a universal testing machine (Autograph AG-IS 150kN, Shimadzu Corp.). The load was applied quasi-statically under displacement control with a crosshead speed of 1.0mm/min. The applied load and the shortening of the platens were collected by digital data acquisition system.

Dynamic crush test

Dynamic crush tests were performed by drop weight impact test to investigate impact speed on energy absorption capability of CFRP with the load-control attachment. The impactor was dropped from the maximum height of 12m, which means that the maximum speed just before impact to the CFRP specimen was about 55km/h. The impact speed of impactor was controlled by adjusting the height.

Test fixture was shown in Figure 2. Impactor had a flat impact face as shown in Figure 2(a). The total weight of the impactor was 65kg. Impact load was collected by load cell (CLP-500KNB, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo. Co., Ltd.). CFRP tube with the load-control attachment was placed on the load cell using the positioning jig. Dynamic crush tests were recorded by high speed camera (Phantom V7.1, Vision Research). Displacement of impactor was measured from the image of high speed camera by using image analysis software (PcVector, OKK Inc).

Figure 2 Test fixture for dynamic crush test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quasi-static compression test

Figure 3 shows load-displacement curves of unidirectional CFRP with the load-control attachment obtained by quasi-static compression tests. In the initial transition region, load dropped after the initial increase due to the local damage of the CFRP. The load again increased up to the sustained load when the load-control attachment had small curvature radius. On the other hands, the load did not increase again in the transition region when the load-control attachment had large curvature radius. After the initial transition region, load kept almost constant under progressive crushing of the CFRP.

In the case of the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 1\text{mm})$, and $(0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$, fluctuation of sustained load was observed. Loosening of curvature constraint at fracture region as compared to the thickness of CFRP made discontinuous fracture of the CFRP, which resulted in the fluctuation of sustained load. On the other hands, it was not observed when the other load-control attachments were used, which was due to the regulated fracture of CFRP by the load-control attachment.

The sustained load increased when the curvature radius of load-control attachment was small. Figure 4 shows comparison of average sustained load and specific energy absorption by curvature constraints of the attachments. Smaller curvature radius showed higher specific energy absorption. The maximum specific energy absorption of 178kJ/kg was obtained when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was used. On the other hands, minimum specific energy absorption of 8kJ/kg was obtained when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$ was used.

Figure 5 shows CFRP tubes after quasi-static compression tests. In the case of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$, fracture mode of CFRP was fiber breakage, delamination and splitting, which resulted in $E_s=178\text{kJ/kg}$. On the other hand, in the case of the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$, CFRP was back to the almost original shape when the load-control attachment was removed, which meant almost no fiber fracture

Figure 3 Load-displacement curves of CFRP with load-control attachment by quasi-static compression tests

Figure 4 Average load P_a and specific energy absorption E_s of CFRP with load-control attachment by quasi-static compression tests

was occurred by the compression. Fracture mode of the CFRP tube was, therefore, delamination and splitting, which resulted in $E_s=8\text{kJ/kg}$. The difference of fracture modes between the CFRPs with the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ and $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$ was fiber fracture. The difference of the specific energy absorptions was about 170kJ/kg , which was dissipated by the fiber fracture. Energy absorption by the CFRP tube was, therefore, exclusively done by fiber fracture. The effect of splitting and delamination on energy absorption was small as compared with that by fiber fracture in the case of the unidirectional CFRP tube.

Energy absorption capability of the CFRP tube could be controlled by changing the amount of fiber fracture. It is, therefore, important to control the amount of fiber fracture under crushing to design crush energy absorbing structure. The load-control attachment can be easily selected using Figure 4 when required energy absorption was determined individually for each automobile.

Smaller curvature radius showed higher specific energy absorption although it was slightly decreased when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 1\text{mm})$ was used. It was considered to indicate maximum specific energy absorption when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$ was used. The load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$ may bent the CFRP of 3mm thickness with smallest curvature. The maximum specific energy absorption was, however, obtained when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was used.

Figure 6 shows cross section of the CFRP with the load-control attachment. Curvature radius of the load-control attachment was $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$. The opening around the outer curvature constrictor of load-control attachment was observed because CFRP could not bend along the outer curvature. Since CFRP was pressed to the inner curvature of the load-control attachment, fiber fracture of the CFRP around inner curvature constrictor increased when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was used, which resulted in higher specific energy absorption than that by the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$. Specific energy absorption was,

$E_s=178\text{kJ/kg}$
(a) $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$

$E_s=108\text{kJ/kg}$
(b) $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$

$E_s=36\text{kJ/kg}$
(c) $(R_o, R_i) = (1\text{mm}, 4\text{mm})$

$E_s=17\text{kJ/kg}$
(d) $(R_o, R_i) = (2\text{mm}, 5\text{mm})$

$E_s=18\text{kJ/kg}$
(e) $(R_o, R_i) = (3\text{mm}, 6\text{mm})$

$E_s=9\text{kJ/kg}$
(f) $(R_o, R_i) = (4\text{mm}, 7\text{mm})$

$E_s=8\text{kJ/kg}$
(g) $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$

Figure 5 CFRP tubes after quasi-static compression tests

(a) Cross sectional picture

(b) Schematics of cross sectional picture

Figure 6 Cross section of CFRP with load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 3\text{mm})$

however, decreased when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 1\text{mm})$ was used. Loosening of constraint by the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 1\text{mm})$ caused large fluctuation of sustained load, which resulted in smaller specific energy absorption as compared to that by the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$.

Dynamic crush test

Dynamic crush tests were performed to investigate the impact speed on energy absorption capability of the CFRP with the load-control attachment. Dynamic crush tests were performed with different impactor speeds of 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 55km/h. The load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was used here.

Figure 7 shows load-displacement curves obtained by the dynamic crush tests. The result by quasi-static compression test was also shown in the figure. Since the impactor hit to jig due to the shortage of the specimen length when the displacement exceeded 60mm, the figure showed until the displacement of 60mm. The impactor hit to jig only when the impact speed was 55km/h.

In the initial transition region, the load showed a modest increase as compared to that by quasi-static compression. It was caused by the inertia of positioning jig between load cell and CFRP tube. Figure 8 shows comparison of average load by impact speed. The average loads were calculated eliminating the initial transition region to evaluate the effect of curvatures of the load-control attachments on energy absorption capability of the CFRP. Average loads were almost constant not dependent on the impact speed. Energy absorption capability of the CFRP with the load-control attachment was irrespective of impact speed.

Figure 9 shows CFRP tubes after dynamic crush test when the impact speed was 35km/h. Fracture modes of the CFRP were fiber fracture, delamination and splitting, which was same with that of CFRP after quasi-static compression test (see Figure 5a). The average load was also same with that by quasi-static compression test. It was

Figure 7 Load-displacement curve of CFRP with load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0, 2\text{mm})$ by dynamic crush test

Figure 8 Comparison of average load by impact speed

Figure 9 CFRP tube after dynamic crush test of 35km/h
(Load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was removed)

reported that the energy absorption capability of CFRP may change by impact speed due to the transition of fracture mode [8-11]. The load-control attachment constrained fracture mode of the CFRP, which resulted in almost same average load irrespective of impact speed.

Figure 10 shows load-displacement curves by dynamic crush test when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$ was used. The load-displacement curve showed almost same with that by quasi-static compression test even when the load-control attachment had large curvature radius.

Figure 11 shows comparison of specific energy absorption of CFRP with the load-control attachments by quasi-static compression and dynamic crush test. Impact speed of the dynamic crush test was 55km/h. Specific energy absorption increased when the curvature radius of the attachment became small, which coincided with the results by quasi-static compression test. Fracture mode was same unrelated to impact speed when the same load-control attachment was used. Since the load-control attachment constrained fracture mode of the CFRP, it was considered that the effect of rate dependence of interlaminar fracture toughness on energy absorption capability of the CFRP became small. Energy absorption capability of the CFRP was almost same irrespective of impact speed when the load-control attachment was applied.

Figure 10 Load-displacement curve of CFRP with load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (5, 8\text{mm})$ by dynamic crush test

Figure 11 Comparison of specific energy absorptions of CFRP with load-control attachment by quasi-static compression and dynamic crush test

CONCLUSIONS

Progressive crushing of unidirectional CFRP tube with load control attachment was investigated under quasi-static compression and dynamic crush test. The results obtained in this study were as follows.

- (1) Minimum specific energy absorption of unidirectional CFRP tube was 8kJ/kg when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (5\text{mm}, 8\text{mm})$ was used. Fracture modes of the CFRP were delamination and splitting.
- (2) Maximum specific energy absorption of unidirectional CFRP tube was 178kJ/kg when the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$ was

used. Fracture modes of the CFRP were fibre fracture, delamination and splitting.

- (3) Specific energy absorption of unidirectional CFRP tube was controlled arbitrary from 8 to 178kJ/kg by changing the curvature of the load-control attachment. The amount of fiber fracture was controlled by the attachment, which resulted in wide range capability of energy absorption of the CFRP.
- (4) Energy absorption of CFRP was exclusively done by the fiber fracture. Smaller curvature radius made larger amount of fiber fracture, which resulted in high specific energy absorption.
- (5) Fluctuation of sustained load was not observed except for the load-control attachment of $(R_o, R_i) = (0\text{mm}, 1\text{mm})$ and $(0\text{mm}, 2\text{mm})$, which was due to the regulated fracture of CFRP by the attachment.
- (6) Designing of energy absorption of CFRP was easy once relationship between curvature of the load-control attachment and specific energy absorption was obtained (see Figure 4).
- (7) Specific energy absorption of the CFRP with the load-control attachment was not dependent on impact speed. Quasi-static compression test were enough to investigate energy absorption capability of CFRP with the load-control attachment.

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